

Aerodynamic Optimization of Freight Trains.

Part 1: Characterization of real-world operation from a full-scale measurement campaign.

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Abstract

The DLR FR8-LAB, a self-contained measurement-system equipped container has been used to take aerodynamic measurements on operational freight-trains. Transient pressure was measured with 330 sensors, and the global transient-forces and moments have been derived: aerodynamic drag – important for operational efficiency, and side-force and rolling moment – important for safety (the risk of overturning and derailment). LiDAR sensors, satellite navigation and thermal cameras are used to couple the aerodynamic measurements with the operating scenarios. Results have indicated significant differences in aerodynamic characteristics based on the operating conditions of freight trains: loading configuration, tunnels, crosswind – that have a significant impact on operating efficiency, and potentially the safety of operation. Together with wind-tunnel experiments performed in parallel – validated by this real-world data – recommendations for aerodynamic optimization can be made for freight-train and infrastructure operators and manufacturers.

Keywords: freight, aerodynamics, drag, crosswind stability, safety

1. Introduction

Aerodynamic resistance, drag, is a primary component of the overall resistance to motion a freight train experiences and therefore very important for energy efficiency. Aerodynamics becomes more important with train speed, so the plans and predictions of operating from 110 to 160 km/h and faster will only increase this importance. Depending on the type of power supply, this affects directly either emissions, or range – both of which are important considerations for current and future freight operation. In addition to drag, crosswind stability – and the resulting risk of overturning – as well as specific interaction with infrastructure like tunnels and bridges and other vehicles, makes freight aerodynamics also important for safety of operation.

Freight-trains operate in a variety of complex conditions that have a strong impact on the aerodynamic characteristics of efficiency and safety; weather, infrastructure and other vehicles - all with various locomotive, wagon and container configurations. It is important therefore, that any recommendations for aerodynamic optimization are based in the reality of such operation, and not solely in idealized conditions. To characterize the real-world aerodynamics, measurements have been performed on a full-scale shipping container, the DLR FR8-LAB, that has been transported on normal operating freight-trains in Europe. The FR8-LAB is a 'swap-body' shipping-container (Fig 1a) fitted with aerodynamic measurement equipment, that can be loaded in different configurations (Bell et al., 2022). The FR8-LAB is self-contained, with an on-board solar-power supply, data-acquisition system and remote-access communication.

This work aims for improved freight-train operational efficiency and safety, through realizable aerodynamic optimization of: freight-train and wagon geometry, loading configuration schemes and infrastructure-vehicle and vehicle-vehicle interaction. Realizable optimization is enabled – and continuously supported and informed from improved understanding of causal flow physics – through the coupling of the real-world measurements from the FR8-LAB that validate state-of-the-art, controlled, scientific wind-tunnel

optimization experiments.

2. Methodology

A bespoke IoT-based data acquisition system was developed for the FR8-LAB to ensure robust and energy efficient operation in the challenging industrial environment. Time-resolved (up to 1000Hz) surface-pressure measurements are performed at 330 positions on the container (Fig 1b). The reference side is open to the interior pressure of the container. Pressure on the front and rear surface is integrated to provide insight into the pressure drag. Longitudinal rows and rings along the side and roof of the container estimate the side force, yaw and roll moments. The pressure measurements locations are selected to resolve the pressure gradients across the surface, and identify the transient pressure signatures of complex turbulent flow structures like the recirculation regions in between containers and flow separation at the roof/sides. This enables accurate predictions of the forces and moments on the container and provides insight into the underlying causal flow physics.

The container's operating conditions are measured by additional sensors (Fig 1c). These conditions are then associated to the measured surface-pressure and corresponding aerodynamic characteristics. A global navigation satellite system (GNSS) determines the location and the velocity over ground (VoG). Seven, single-point LiDAR distance sensors with ~40m range are located on the container's sides, roof and front/rear surface to quantitatively characterize the physical environment at high temporal resolution sampling rates of up to 1000Hz. Two additional LiDAR sensors point at the ground, and are also used to determine VoG. Two wide-angle 75° field-of-view (FoV) thermal cameras (able to operate at night and in poor weather conditions) provide additional qualitative information on the local topography. Accelerometers, barometric pressure and temperature sensors measure the conditions inside the container.

Figure 1: a. The DLR FR8-LAB loaded onto a wagon in an operational freight-train consist. b. The location of surface-pressure measurements. c. Environmental sensors: 7 x LiDAR (red), 2 x LiDAR VOG (orange), 2 x thermal cameras (green) and accelerometers (purple).

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3. Results

The average surface-pressure distribution measured during an example measurement (Fig 2) show high pressure at the front surface of the FR8-LAB and low pressure at the roof and side front edges caused by stagnated and separated flow respectively. The measured pressure on the surfaces of the container are integrated to estimate the global aerodynamic forces and moments acting on the container (illustrated in Fig 2b). The potential operational envelope of global forces, and thus efficiency and safety can then be mapped for many possible conditions. One such example, is the effect loading configuration has on efficiency.

The surface pressure distributions (mean and standard deviation) and probability distribution of aerodynamic drag for a number of example cases with different loading configurations are presented in Figure 3 and 4 respectively. The local loading configurations presented corresponds to gaps either side of the container from 1.6 to >30m; ranging from the typical gap between containers on different wagons to gaps the size of multiple containers. Clear differences in the mean and fluctuating surface pressure are observable for different loading configurations. At the smallest gap, the entire front surface doesn't experience high pressure, only the upper and outer edges, and negligible separation and low pressure exists on the side and top edges. For the larger gaps the distribution is the same as the example in Figure 2, whilst the magnitude of the pressure increases with increasing gap. At the largest gap, the entire front surface sees high fluctuations, rather than just the edges. The aerodynamic drag coefficient also varies significantly with loading configuration, with means of $c_D = 0.17$ to 0.4 (>100% increase) with corresponding increasing standard deviations of $\sigma_{c_D} = 0.04$ - 0.13 .

Similar sensitivity of aerodynamic drag to freight-train loading configuration have previously been observed in field-tests (Quazi et al., 2023), wind-tunnel experiments (Buhr et al., 2024, Siegel et al., 2024) and numerical simulations (Maleki et al., 2019). The examples presented are in 'clean' operating condition; no significant infrastructure interaction such as tunnels, large bridges or exposure to crosswind are included. Further, in these examples presented, the FR8-LAB was loaded in the approximate middle of the train consist (situated away from any local effects from the start and end of the train). Such operating conditions have already been observed to have significant effects on the aerodynamic loads, in addition to the loading configuration – these effects, as well as side-force and rolling moments are important for safety of operation. These results demonstrate that part of the aerodynamic operational envelope for real-world freight-trains have successfully been mapped.

These experiments are the first time high-spatial/high-temporally resolved surface pressure measurements have been made on a shipping container coupled with synchronized environmental measurements (cameras, LIDARs, accelerometers). This results in real-world aerodynamic drag (resistance) and side-force/moments (safety) assessments to be obtained both in general terms as well as for specific important aerodynamic operating scenarios such as through tunnels or over bridges. This

Figure 2: a. Surface pressure distribution overlaid on the real FR8-LAB and the corresponding b. Resulting local and global force vectors and moments.

enables validation of wind-tunnel aerodynamic optimization – which is performed in parallel with this full-scale experimental campaign and presented at WCRR2025 in “Aerodynamic Optimization of Freight Trains. Part 2: Efficiency and safety recommendations from validated wind-tunnel experiments” - as well as insight into the flow physics for improved understanding of aerodynamic phenomena that exist in real-world operation.

Figure 3: Mean surface-pressure distributions from a. front and b. rear views, and standard deviation of surface-pressure c. front and d. rear views respectively for four example ‘clean’ measurements (no apparent crosswind, or infrastructure, vehicle interaction) with increasing front gap distances. Example #1 front gap $f_G=1.62$, rear gap $r_G=8.6$ m, #2: $f_G=8.6$, $r_G=1.6$ m, #3: $f_G=14.76$, $r_G=1.65$ m, #4: $f_G>30$ m, $r_G=14$ m.

Figure 4: Density distribution of aerodynamic drag, C_D , of four example measurements with increasing front gap distances. Example #1 front gap $f_G=1.62$, rear gap $r_G=8.6$ m, #2: $f_G=8.6$, $r_G=1.6$ m, #3: $f_G=14.76$, $r_G=1.65$ m, #4: $f_G>30$ m, $r_G=14$ m.

freight train to be affected. In Figure 5, the mean and standard deviation of the surface-pressure distribution is presented for an example of apparent crosswind exposure. Clear asymmetry is visible in both the mean and fluctuating pressure, with higher pressure coupled with higher fluctuations on the right (windward) front surface. The windward side surface also exhibits a region of high fluctuation, with a small region of low pressure, in contrast, the leeward side surface exhibits a larger low-pressure region albeit of slightly higher pressure, and lower fluctuating values. This apparent crosswind example case corresponded to an increase in aerodynamic drag from $C_D\sim 0.4$ to 0.6 and a side-force coefficient of $C_S\sim 1.7$. The local loading configuration of the FR8-LAB in this case was a front gap of >30 m and rear gap of 1.68 m

Figure 5: Example of asymmetric surface pressure distribution: mean and standard deviation during apparent crosswind exposure, with front gap of >30 m and rear gap of 1.68 m. Aerodynamic drag, increases from $C_D\sim 0.4$ to 0.6 during apparent crosswind, with a side-force coefficient of $C_S\sim 1.7$.

Transient snapshots of the surface-pressure distribution on the front surfaces during an example tunnel entry is presented in Figure 6. In this case, the local loading configuration of the FR8-LAB was a front gap of 8 m and rear gap of 1.68 m. As the container enters the tunnel, indicated at $t=0$, the front pressure shows increasing pressure of $C_P\sim 0.5$ to >1 , with increasing magnitude of low pressure on the front side and roof edges of $C_P\sim -0.25$ to -0.5 . Additional transient fluctuations on all surfaces are visible. These pressure changes correspond to an aerodynamic drag increases from $C_D\sim 0.2$ - to >0.4 once inside tunnel.

Figure 6: Example of transient surface pressure distribution during tunnel entry, with front gap of 8m and rear gap of 1.68m. Aerodynamic drag increases from $c_D \sim 0.2$ to >0.4 once inside tunnel.

5. Conclusion

An on-rail measurement campaign has been performed from January-October 2024 on the European rail network, in particular in Spain, over different routes and across a variety of operating scenarios. Results so far have indicated significant differences in aerodynamic characteristics based on the operating conditions of freight trains: loading configuration, tunnels, bridges, crosswind – that have a significant impact on operating efficiency, and potentially safety of operation. Together with wind-tunnel experiments performed in parallel – validated by this real-world data – recommendations for aerodynamic optimization are made for freight train operators such as RENFE and ADIF and manufacturers.

The FR8-LAB is a platform available for collaboration with future research/engineering experiments requiring on-rail measurements. The data is currently, and can be used for validation of future experimental/numerical investigations from other research groups, not limited to aerodynamics. This work already exists in a framework of international collaboration, as it is part of the Europe's Rail Flagship Project 5 – TRANS4M-R, which involves many international partners – specifically DLR, RENFE, ADIF and CEIT who are directly involved in improving the efficiency and safety of operation of freight-trains.

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